

EVALUATING NURSES' DISASTER PREPAREDNESS: A COMPARATIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE HOSPITALS OF ISLAMABAD, PAKISTAN

Sakina Attaria^{*1}, Daizi Jafar², Sadia Bibi³, Farhat Ullah⁴, Hassan Masood⁵, Saher Sabeen⁶, Allen Cruis⁷, Saina Kiran⁸, Maaz Khan⁹

¹Rawal general and dental hospital, Islamabad, Pakistan.

²Dr. Akbar Niazi Teaching Hospital, Islamabad Pakistan.

³Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital, Islamabad Pakistan.

⁴Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences Islamabad, Pakistan.

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Corresponding Author: *

Sakina Attaria

Abstract

Background:

Disaster preparedness is an essential part of hospital resilience that requires coordinated responses from healthcare professionals who are at the forefront. Nurses make the largest workforce in hospitals, and they play a pivotal role in all phases of disaster management. However, limited disaster-specific training and institutional preparedness continue to challenge effective response in many healthcare settings.

Objective:

To assess the disaster preparedness among registered nurses in Tertiary Care Hospitals of Islamabad and to compare preparedness level between both public and private hospital settings.

Materials and Methods: This was a comparative cross-sectional study conducted in September 2025 among 300 registered nurses selected through simple convenience sampling from two public and two private tertiary care hospitals. Data was collected using a validated questionnaire.

Descriptive statistics, and inferential statistics including independent t-tests, and one-way ANOVA were performed using SPSS version 26.0.

Results:

Overall disaster preparedness was moderate ($M = 3.31$, $SD = \pm 0.96$). Among domains, knowledge scored highest [$M = 3.49$ ($SD \pm 1.066$)], followed by attitude [$M = 3.32$ ($SD \pm 1.17$)], and practice [$M = 3.12$ ($SD \pm 1.05$)], Nurses in public hospitals reported significantly higher knowledge, attitude, and overall preparedness than those in private hospitals ($p < .05$). No notable differences were found by gender or years of experience ($p > .05$).

Conclusion:

Nurses demonstrated moderate disaster preparedness showing stronger grasp of theoretical concepts than practical skills. To improve the level of preparedness among nurses, hospital-based disaster training programs, regular simulation drills, and adequate administrative support collectively helps in increasing nurses' competency and ensuring effective disaster response within healthcare settings.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Disasters are sudden, unpredictable events that disrupt the normal life, causing human, material, economic and environmental losses that are greater than the capacity of the affected community.” (1). Disasters, whether natural or man-made, have a very serious impact on the lives of people, infrastructure, health care services, and the economy, often leading to major losses for both the government and the public (2). Disasters can arise from various sources, natural events including floods, earthquakes, storms, droughts, and disease outbreaks and scientific or technological incidents such as structural failures, explosions, and radiation leaks or civil and political crises including terrorism, strikes, and biological warfare (3,4). The 2022 World Disasters Report by the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies underscored the critical importance of disaster preparedness, response, and recovery, especially in the context of public health emergencies, drawing conclusion from the global experience during the COVID-19 pandemic (5). Asia is among one of the most affected regions of the world by such events, not only in terms of number of occurrences but also resulting fatalities due to disasters (6). According to the World Disasters Report 2015, Asia alone accounts for nearly half of all global disasters that occurred in 2014 (7). Pakistan in particular has experienced increased exposure to such intense and frequent catastrophic events over the last 15 years. These include floods, earthquakes, epidemics, and infrastructure collapses (8). Such events test the resilience of healthcare systems and demand coordinated responses, particularly from frontline health workers. Nurses play vital role in such situations as they are among the ones to respond first and save lives, they need to have the right knowledge, practical skills, and the right attitude. However, research shows that nurses generally have only a moderate level of disaster preparedness. Unfortunately, due to inadequate training, outdated or insufficient equipment, and staff shortages, all of which make it even more difficult for them to manage disaster situations effectively (11,12).

Despite the increase in the regularity and increasing intensity of such catastrophes in Pakistan, nurses

show low levels of preparedness to overcome such situations effectively. Nurses need to be not only aware of the fundamental principles of disaster management, including risk identification and rapid response, but also capable of following leadership protocols and managing uncertainty with competence (13). Study shows that if the nurses get proper training and education, it can significantly improve the knowledge and disaster management among nurses, so there should be continued education and training to enhance and modify their skills for such emergencies (14). Various studies have already assessed the levels of preparedness among nurses in different regions of Pakistan, and all these studies have highlighted the importance of nurses in management of such mass casualties (15,16,17).

There is a study that shows the hospital preparedness for such events. However, there is a noticeable gap and a lack of comprehensive research focused on preparedness levels specifically among nurses in the Capital city Islamabad, Pakistan (18). This Monsoon season 2025, Islamabad faced heavy rainfall 124% more rainfall than July 2024, which lead to sudden flash floods causing over 250 deaths and vast urban disruption (19). The casualties including The Chahan Dam breach and the flooding of major hospitals exposed that there is a significant need to address all these deficits in the emergency response and healthcare system preparedness (20, 21). These recent casualties highlighted the urgent need to assess the disaster preparedness among nurses, who are among the frontline healthcare workers. This will help to implement evidence-based support to improve disaster planning, response training, and overall healthcare resilience in the Capital city.

Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess the level of disaster preparedness among nurses in Tertiary Care Hospitals of Islamabad, including both private and public sector hospitals.

2. MATERIALS & METHODS

2.1. Study Design and Setting

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in September 2025 across four Hospitals. Two Private and Two Public Tertiary Care Hospitals were selected from the Capital city of Pakistan which included Rawal General and Dental Hospital, Dr.

Akbar Niazi Teaching Hospital, Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital, Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences (PIMS) respectively. Two Private, Teaching Tertiary Care Hospitals included Rawal General and Dental hospital a 500-bedded and Dr. Akbar Niazi Teaching Hospital 500-bedded hospitals. Two Public, Teaching Tertiary Care Hospitals included Federal Government Polyclinic Hospital a 585-bedded, and Pakistan institute of medical sciences 1254-bedded hospitals.

2.2. Study Population and Sampling Approach

2.2.1. Study Population

Study participants included registered nurses (RNs), general nurses holding a nursing diploma, and specialist nurses with at least six months of professional experience. Participants who voluntarily agreed to participate were included while Individuals who declined participation were excluded. Nursing students and paramedical staff were also excluded to maintain the study's focus on frontline clinical nursing staff.

2.2.2. Sampling technique and sample size

Participants were selected using a simple convenience sampling technique. To determine the required sample size, Slovin's formula was applied. The total population of (N = 1200) nurses working across the selected four hospitals with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error was used.

The calculated sample size was 300 participants. A proportionate distribution of the sample was made across the four hospitals, 75 from each hospital making all together 150 nurses from Private and 150 nurses from public sector hospitals. This approach allowed the inclusion of equal number of nurses from both sectors and ensured adequate representation from both public and private sectors. Eligible participants were full-time employees of the selected hospitals. Data collection was helped through the hospital administration and departmental heads to identify required participants.

2.3. Data collection

Data was collected using a self-structured questionnaire that was adapted from previous study

conducted by [Vishba and Shaheen \(2025\)](#). The questionnaire evaluated the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of the nurses regarding disaster readiness. To ensure understanding and prevent misunderstandings, participants were given clear explanation for every question.

2.4. Ethical Review

The ethical review was obtained from Institutional Review Board of Rawal Institute of Health Sciences, Islamabad (Letter No. RIHS/IRB/44/2025). The potential participants were contacted through meeting in person and were informed about the study and how their data would be recorded, managed, and used. Participants were fully informed about the aims of the study, and their written consent was secured prior to starting data collection.

2.5. Data analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0.

- **Descriptive statistics** showed the demographics of the participants details and how they responded.
- **Inferential statistics** included independent samples t-test and was used to compare the levels of preparedness in public and private hospitals.
- The **Pearson correlation coefficient** examined the association among knowledge, attitudes, practices, and demographic variables.
- Results were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

There were total of 300 nurses in the study. Of these, 52.3% (n = 157) were women and 47.7% (n = 143) were men. Most nurses (60.7%, n = 182) were aged between 21 and 31 years. When looking at work experience, 61.7% (n = 185) had been in the profession for one to five years. Educationally, 21% (n = 63) were diploma holders, 55% (n = 165) had a BSN, 19% (n = 57) had a post-RN BScN, and 5% (n = 15) had completed a postgraduate MSN degree. The detailed description of the demographic data is given below in Table 1.

Table 1: Description of Demographic Data

		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	143	47.7%
	Female	157	52.3%
Age	< 20 years	21	7.0%
	21-30	182	60.7%
	31-40	64	21.3%
	41-50	31	10.3%
	>50 years	2	0.7%
Level of Education	Diploma	63	21.0%
	BSN generic	165	55.0%
	Post-RN BScN	57	19.0%
	MSN (post-graduate)	15	5.0%
Level of Experience	<1 year	57	19.0%
	1-5 years	185	61.7%
	6-10 years	29	9.7%
	>10 years	29	9.7%

3.1. Knowledge

Using a five-point Likert scale, the average knowledge score was 3.49 (SD = 1.06). Most nurses (61.6%) believed that disaster management is a vital part of healthcare services, while a smaller group (19.7%) did not share this view and strongly disagreed. Only about a third of the nurses (37.7%) said they were well aware of their hospital’s disaster management plan, and just over half (53.7%) said they understood their roles during such situations.

62% of respondents acknowledged having some understanding of triage procedures, whereas 65.4% were knowledgeable how to prevent infections during such emergencies. But 57% of people are aware of emergency codes along with only a moderate level of knowledge about patient evacuation procedures was indicated by 59.7% of respondents. About 55.7% of respondents claimed to be aware of their hospital’s disaster policies, and 55% reported having ever taken part in formal disaster training. The weakest sections were connected to the handling of emergency equipment, and hospital policies, demonstrated the necessity of consistent and targeted

training meetings for nurses (refer to Table 2 for more information).

3.2. Attitudes

The mean score for attitude domain was 3.32 (SD = 1.17). This indicates a generally favourable but moderate attitude towards being prepared for emergencies. 57.6% of nurses said they were confident in their ability to function well in disaster situations, and the majority 59.7% agreed or strongly agreed that disaster management training is crucial. Similarly, 57.4% of respondents favoured adding disaster management to the nursing curriculum and 53.6% stressed the value of ongoing disaster education.

Effective leadership enhances disaster response, according to 51.7% of respondents while also had a positive opinion of teamwork and collaboration during disasters. However, opinions regarding institutional preparedness were divided; organizational confidence was lacking, as only 50.7% of respondents trusted their hospital’s preparedness for disasters. Overall, nurses valued teamwork and

disaster training but because of uneven institutional participation in disaster planning, attitudinal uncertainty persisted (see Table 3 for details).

3.3. Practices

With a mean score of 3.12 (SD = 1.05) the practice domain showed the lowest levels of readiness. This implies a low level of involvement in actual or simulated disaster related activities. 53.7% of respondents said that they had clearly defined roles during drills, while only 43% of respondents regularly participated in them. 49% of respondents agreed that accurate documentation is crucial during disasters, and 49.3% of respondents reported

knowing where and how to use emergency equipment.

At 48.7% and 55.3%, respectively, participation in infection control and patient evacuation protocols was moderate. Just 41.4% had participated in any official disaster preparedness training while 36% of respondents strongly disagreed and they had demonstrated triage procedures during drills, 25.3% of respondents strongly disagreed with updating themselves on hospital disaster policies. These results show that while there is conceptual understanding, there is still a lack of consistent practical engagement, with little regular participation in drills, debriefings and continuous preparedness efforts (see Table 4 for details)

Table 2: Description of percentages of knowledge scores

Questions	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
1. Disaster management is an essential part of healthcare.	19.7	11.3	7.3	27.3	34.3
2. I can list three types of disasters commonly encountered in healthcare settings.	23	10	31.3	10	25.7
3. I am familiar with the hospital's current disaster management plan.	21	9	15	17.3	37.7
4. I understand the roles and responsibilities of nurses in the event of a disaster.	20.3	4.3	21.7	15	38.7
5. The communication channels during a disaster are effective.	15	8	22.7	12	42.3
6. I know how to perform triage during a disaster.	16.7	9	12.3	19.3	42.7
7. I am aware of the emergency codes used during disasters.	12.7	12.7	17.7	14.7	42.3
8. I know how to evacuate patients during a disaster.	13.0	12.7	14.7	30	29.7
9. I understand infection control procedures during disasters.	10.3	9	15.3	31.7	33.7
10. I can identify vulnerable populations during a disaster.	10.7	8	20	32.3	28.3
11. I know how to document patient care during disasters.	11.7	10	12	35	31.3
12. I understand the chain of command during disaster response.	14.7	8.3	15.7	37.7	23.7

13. I am aware of my hospital's disaster policies and procedures.	14.3	9	21	21	34.7
14. I have received formal training on disaster management.	17.3	11.7	16	24.3	30.7
15. I can identify the correct use of emergency equipment during a disaster.	18.7	9.3	23	22	27

Table 3: Description of percentages of Attitude scores

Questions	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
1. Disaster management training is essential for all staff nurses.	21.7	11.3	7.3	22	37.7
2. I am confident in my ability to perform effectively during a disaster.	18.3	10.3	13.7	25.3	32.3
3 The staff collaborates well during disaster situations.	19.7	13	17.3	21.3	28.7
4. Continuous education on disaster management is necessary.	20.7	8.7	17	16.3	37.3
5. Emotional well-being of patients is adequately addressed during a disaster.	19.7	10.7	17.7	24.7	27.3
6. I feel prepared to take immediate action during a disaster.	23.3	7.3	10	25	34.3
7. Disaster management should be a part of the nursing curriculum.	17.7	14	11	23.7	33.7
8. I believe regular mock drills enhance preparedness.	23.3	9.3	17.7	18	31.7
9. I am motivated to improve my disaster management skills.	21	10.3	13.7	25.3	29.7
10. I trust my institution's preparedness for disasters.	23.7	11.3	14.3	22.7	28
11. Teamwork is essential in effective disaster response	23.7	11	13.7	20	31.7
12. Effective leadership improves disaster response.	21.3	9.3	17.7	22.3	29.3
13. Disaster response is a shared responsibility among healthcare professionals.	19.7	11.3	20.7	22.3	26
14. Caring for disaster victims is an important nursing responsibility.	20.7	11.7	9.7	21.7	36.3

Table 4: Description of percentages of practice scores

Questions	Strongly disagree (%)	Disagree (%)	Neutral (%)	Agree (%)	Strongly Agree (%)
1. I participate regularly in disaster drills.	22.3	15.7	19	25	18
2. My roles and responsibilities during disaster drills are clearly defined.	21.7	14.7	10	24.7	29
3. I am familiar with the location and use of equipment in the department.	22.7	10.7	17.3	26	23.3
4. I have provided feedback on the disaster management processes.	22.7	13.7	18.7	22.7	22.3
5. Accurate documentation during a disaster is crucial for patient care.	21.3	11.7	18	16	33
6. I follow infection control procedures during disasters.	21.3	14	16	22.7	26
7. I assist in evacuating patients during a disaster.	16.7	11	17	28.3	27
8. I am involved in post-disaster debriefing sessions.	19	15	17	22	27
9. I attend training programs on disaster preparedness.	25	12	21.7	15.7	25.7
10. I help in identifying at-risk patients during emergencies.	21.3	13.7	16	27.7	21.3
11. I follow hospital protocols during disaster events.	27	10.7	16	18.3	28
12. I update myself on hospital disaster policies regularly.	25.3	12	21.3	18.7	22.7
13. I am alert and responsive during simulated disaster scenarios.	22.3	11	22.7	22.7	21.3
14. I can demonstrate proper triage procedures during a drill.	36	8.7	17.7	19.3	18.3

The nurses achieved an overall mean disaster preparedness score of 3.31 (SD = 0.96), which suggests a moderate level of readiness. Among the domains, the knowledge score was highest (M = 3.49, SD = 1.07), followed by attitude (M = 3.33, SD = 1.18) and practice (M = 3.12, SD = 1.06). These

findings suggest that while nurses demonstrated reasonable conceptual awareness of disaster management, their practical engagement and participation in training and drills remained limited as shown below in [Table 5](#), and graphical representation showing mean scores of preparedness components in [Figure 1](#).

Table 5: Description of Overall-preparedness and KAP means

Mean	Total	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Knowledge mean	300	1.00	5.00	3.4907	1.06638
Attitude mean	300	1.00	5.00	3.3288	1.17836
Practices mean	300	1.00	5.00	3.1229	1.05745
Overall-preparedness mean	300	1.00	5.00	3.3141	0.96418

Figure 1: Mean scores of (preparedness components) knowledge, attitude and practices

Comparative analysis revealed that nurses in public hospitals had significantly higher mean scores for knowledge (M = 3.78, SD = 1.01), attitude (M = 3.55, SD = 1.16), and overall preparedness (M = 3.51, SD = 0.96) than those in private hospitals (M = 3.21, SD = 1.05; M = 3.11, SD = 1.16; M = 3.11, SD = 0.93, respectively) ($p < .05$). Differences in practice scores were not statistically

significant ($p = .125$). Graphical representation of difference between KAP means of both sector hospitals are shown in (Figure 2) and overall-preparedness mean score for both sector hospitals in (Figure 3) respectively. Gender-wise comparison showed that male nurses scored slightly higher than females in all domains, but the differences were not statistically significant ($p > .05$)

Figure 2: Comparative analysis of KAP means of Public & Private Hospitals

Figure 3: Comparative analysis of overall preparedness between Public & Private Hospitals

4. DISCUSSION

Findings of this study revealed that registered nurses in Tertiary Care Hospitals of Islamabad are

moderately prepared for disasters. This pattern is consistent with findings from earlier studies, which reported similar mid-level readiness among nurses in

Asian healthcare settings (22, 23). The higher scores in knowledge contrast to practice were found. This shows that while nurses understand fundamental disaster management concepts such as infection control, triage, and emergency communication, but mostly lack the opportunity to apply this knowledge in real or simulated scenarios. This finding points to the limited availability of organized training sessions and practice drills in many hospitals as shown in Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4 respectively.

According to the study, nurses working in public hospitals were more equipped to handle emergencies than those in private hospitals. They work under more defined disaster plans, deal with emergencies more frequently, and have greater institutional support for training, which is probably why they are better prepared. Previous research has also shown that public-sector nurses tend to be more involved in drills and have better disaster management training opportunities (24). Since there were no significant differences between gender and years of experience, disaster preparedness is more closely related to institutional opportunities for practice-based learning and continuing education than it is to demographic factors. This demonstrates that all nurses, regardless of their experience level, should participate in standardized disaster management programs in order to maintain current and consistent preparedness skills over time.

In short, the results show that hospitals need to make disaster preparedness a part of their policies and management. Regular practice drills, better communication between departments, and active involvement from leaders are all important steps. Previous research has indicated that incorporating disaster management into continuous professional development (CPD) programs can enhance nurses' confidence and preparedness for actual emergency scenarios (25, 26).

5. CONCLUSION

The results showed that nurses had a good understanding of disaster concepts, but they weren't very good at using these ideas in real situations. Nurses who work in public hospitals performed better than those who work in private hospitals. This is mainly because the two types of hospitals train and

prepare their staff for emergencies in different ways. On the other hand, gender and work experience didn't seem to matter much, which shows that regular training is more important for improving skills than factors like gender and work experience. Hospitals need to do more than just to be aware of how to get ready for disasters; they need to take continuous action. Hospitals can do this by setting-up regular mock drills, hands-on training sessions, and workshops to help nurses remember what they learned. With the right resources, clear rules, and support from hospital management, nurses can work together to be prepared for any kind of emergency. The study yielded significant insights; however, its findings were constrained by dependence on self-reported data, potentially affected by social desirability and recall bias. The study was conducted in only four tertiary care hospitals of the Capital city, and the results may not represent nurses working in primary and secondary care hospitals. The use of cross-sectional study design represented a snapshot in time and may not reflect the changes in preparedness that occurs overtime following training interventions, emphasizing the need for longitudinal designs, and observational assessments to better evaluate performance in real-life disaster situations in future research.

AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTION

¹**Sakina Attaria:** Substantial Contribution to study design, securing permission for data collection, data analysis, Manuscript Writing, managed submission and correspondence.

²**Daizi Jafar:** Conceptualized and supervised the overall study, guidance throughout the research process, providing guidance and critically reviewed the final manuscript.

³**Sadia Bibi:** Co-supervised and contributed to study design, data interpretation and manuscript review.

⁴**Farhat Ullah:** Contributed in developing the methodology, obtaining permission for data collection, and actively participated in data collection.

⁵**Hassan Masood:** Contributed to data collection and data entry for analysis.

⁶**Saher Sabeen:** Contributed in securing permission for data collection, and took part in data collection.

⁷**Allen Cruis:** Contributed to data collection

⁸**Saina Kiran:** Contributed to obtaining permission for data collection, helped in data collection and data entry

⁹**Maaz Khan:** Contributed in data collection.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

RN's – Registered nurses

PIMS – Pakistan Institute of Medical Sciences

KAP – Knowledge, Attitudes, and Practices

IRB –Institutional Review Board

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declared None

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